

A High-Performance Framework for Large-Scale 5G/6G Terrestrial Coverage Simulation

Emiliano Pallotti Manuel Faccioli

Federica Mangiatordi

Fondazione Ugo Bordoni

Viale del Policlinico 147, Rome, Italy

{epallotti,mfaccioli,fmangiatordi}@fub.it

Abstract

This work introduces a high-performance computing (HPC) framework for large-scale simulation of 5G and future 6G terrestrial wireless signal coverage. The system is designed to efficiently support multiple propagation models and manage tens of thousands of transmitters with heterogeneous radio electric characteristics. It incorporates advanced indexing techniques to organize and retrieve transmitter data efficiently, minimising memory access latency and accelerating spatial queries. By leveraging parallel multiprocessor architectures and optimized data handling, the framework significantly reduces the computational complexity of current solutions, enabling the generation of large-area coverage maps within seconds and supporting evaluations up to 26 GHz. Performance assessments show a drastic reduction in simulation time and approximately 91.4% lower energy consumption, confirming the framework’s suitability for national-scale electromagnetic field (EMF) assessments and large-scale data processing in mobile radio networks.

Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM). This manuscript has been accepted for presentation at the International Congress on Ultra Modern Telecommunications and Control Systems (ICUMT 2025). The final published version may differ in formatting.

Keywords: Parallel Programming, HPC, Radio Propagation, wireless simulation, 5G/6G, spatial query.

1 Introduction

The evolution of mobile networks towards 6G is one of the key pillars of the strategy for developing sustainable cloud services and mission-critical Industry 4.0 applications, such as digital twins and predictive maintenance. 5G/6G technologies will support the growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) by enabling more efficient resource management and enhancing public services. These advancements are enabled by ultra-reliable, low-latency communications (URLLC), enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC) [1]. To meet the demanding capacity and latency requirements of these communication services, next-generation networks must exploit high-frequency spectrum bands. Consequently, evaluating and optimising wireless signal coverage over large geographical regions becomes critical for both infrastructure planning and regulatory compliance.

However, traditional radio propagation tools, especially those used in research or network planning environments, are often not designed to compute wireless coverage over large-scale areas—such as entire national territories—while simultaneously accounting for tens of thousands of transmitting antennas [2]. These antennas may differ significantly in terms of frequency

bands, propagation models, and radioelectric characteristics such as transmission power, gain, and antenna radiation patterns. As a result, the joint evaluation of such heterogeneous parameters across vast regions often results in extremely long simulation times, limiting the practical applicability of these tools for high-resolution, large-scale network assessments.

To address this problem, this paper presents a high-performance computing (HPC) 5G/6G simulation tool. This framework is designed to simulate 5G/6G signal coverage of networks with heterogeneous terrestrial transmitters across national territories, offering greater speed and efficiency. The proposed solution utilises multithreaded processing, efficient geospatial data structures, and mathematical simplifications to reduce computational overhead while maintaining accuracy significantly. The proposed *HPC 5G/6G simulator* can handle data sets covering hundreds of thousands of square kilometres and over 100,000 5G/6G transmitters. It supports simulation frequencies of up to 26 GHz, covering both the sub-6 GHz and millimetre wave bands. Key highlights of this work are:

- A novel *GeoQuadTree* data structure, providing a geodetic-aware quadtree indexing method optimised for transmitter locations in NR/6G coverage analysis.
- A *hybrid range-query mechanism* combining planar and Haversine computations with adaptive pruning for large-scale evaluation.
- A *national-scale HPC pipeline* for EMF computation, incorporating entropic load balancing and multi-thread scaling.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the coverage simulation problem and propagation models. Section 3 discusses optimization strategies including parallelization, spatial indexing, and algebraic simplifications. Section 4 details the system architecture and input-output structure. Section 5 presents a comprehensive performance evaluation, and Section 6 concludes the paper with key findings and future directions.

2 Coverage Map problem

2.1 Propagation Model

The propagation models employed in the proposed *HPC simulation tool* account for the complete set of radioelectric parameters associated with each antenna sector. These include the sector's geographical coordinates, radiated power, height above ground, antenna gain, azimuth, tilt, antenna model, frequency, and radiation pattern. Furthermore, the model incorporates environmental and topographical information along the propagation path between the transmitter (site) and the receiver (pixel), such as terrain orography and clutter classification at both link endpoints.

The simulation area is divided into square pixels $l \times l$ meters according to a regular grid, and the electromagnetic power received at the centre of each pixel is assumed to be representative of the entire pixel area.

To perform the path loss calculation, the altimetry data are extracted from the SRTM altimetric database (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission), having a resolution of 90 meters [3], the value is sampled with a regular step from transmitter to receiver point. The propagation model depends on the frequency range, below or above 3 GHz, used by the sector to transmit toward users. The path loss $PL_{[dB]}$ is the sum of three components:

- L_{Stat} an empirical-statistical model that takes into account the characteristics of propagation in different land use scenarios;
- L_{Diff} a deterministic model used for calculation of the attenuation produced by the diffraction relative to the orography;

- L_{Gt} represents the loss in dB of the radiation pattern with respect to the maximum gain Gt in the direction of the junction between the base station and the reception point.

2.2 ITU-R SM.2028-2 Model

Below 3GHz the propagation model used is described in Report ITU-R SM.2028-2 [4], that is an Extended-Hata model derived from COST 231 Action [5] for:

- three frequency range (150-1500 MHz, 1.5-2GHz and 2-3 GHz);
- distances up to 100 km (40 km recommended);
- frequency from 150 MHz to 3 GHz;
- terminal height from 1 m to 200 m.

Another relevant parameter is the scenario where the receivers are located (Dense Urban, Urban, Suburban and Rural) that leads to different clutter correction factors of path loss.

2.3 ITU-R M.2412-0 Model

For frequency above 3 GHz the implemented model is based on Report ITU-R M.2412-0 [6] a “Guidelines for evaluation of radio interface technologies for IMT-2020”. It’s a statistical model specifically identified for the study of IMT-2020 network development scenarios, which does not consider the curvature of the earth, and uses the average height of buildings (h) and the average width of roads (W) to characterize the environments considered. The two specific path loss for Urban Macro (UMa) and Rural Macro (RMa) implemented and used with specific parameter (W, h) in order to cover the four scenarios. The frequency upper limit is not limited to 3 but can reach up to 100 GHz; this makes it feasible to analyze coverage in the recent 26 GHz operating bands. The COST 231 model, suitably calibrated for the reference scenarios (chosen the values of W, h, h_{BS} and h_{UT}), can be adapted to the propagation model defined in the ITU-R Report M.2412-0.

2.4 ITU-R P.526 Model

The ITU-R P.526 [7] recommendation provides different methodologies to evaluate the contribution of attenuation of the L_{Diff} diffraction on the received field, according to the different types of obstacles and possible paths. The diffraction phenomenon mainly depends on the obstruction of the propagation path due to:

- spherical surface of the earth;
- roughness of the ground.

The calculation of the diffraction involves evaluating the elevation profile of the propagation path in the vertical plane based on the following parameters:

- radius of curvature of the earth;
- height of obstacles;
- atmospheric refractive index.

The diffraction attenuation calculation methodology depends on the method used for selecting the obstacles present in the propagation path, in particular the ITU-R P.526-11 [7] version indicate for the evaluation of obstacles the Deygout method, which involves the identification of a group of significant obstacles in the propagation path between the TX transmitter and RX

receiver.

The first step consists of the identification of a main obstacle between TX and RX; afterwards two sub-paths are identified, the first between TX and main obstacle and the second between main obstacle and RX, for which the same procedure of the first path is applied. In this way, a maximum of 3 obstacles are obtained on the basis of which the total diffraction attenuation is calculated.

The last version of ITU-R P.526 [7], reviewed in 2018, sees a variation in the method of defining and selecting obstacles for calculating the diffraction attenuation, by replacing Deygout method with Bullington method, however the ITU-R P.526 version 11 with Deygout method is the version in use in the simulation object of the current discussion.

3 Computational Optimization

The proposed framework for rapid large-scale electromagnetic field (EMF) analysis across the national domain is founded on three core acceleration strategies: multithreading and data separation, quad-tree indexing of TX locations, and algebraic simplification.

3.1 Multithreading and Data Separation Strategy

To ensure that extensive electromagnetic field (EMF) assessments can be carried out across nationwide territories, the proposed framework uses a parallel processing strategy that utilises both multithreading and the data separation principle [8, 9].

The geographical area under study is mapped onto a regular grid of square pixels with side length $l_p = 100$ m, resulting in a resolution of 100 pixels per km^2 . For the Italian territory, this discretisation yields a total of approximately 30 million pixels. Let N_{pix} represent the total number of pixels and T denote the number of threads on the host machine. The entire collection of pixels is divided into T distinct subsets, each containing approximately N_{pix}/T pixels. Each subset is processed independently by a dedicated thread. This static load balancing strategy eliminates thread contention and scheduling overhead, ensures uniform thread usage, and simplifies memory management.

Formally, let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_T\}$ be the partition of the pixel set and $\Phi(p_i)$ the EMF evaluation function on partition p_i . The global coverage map \mathcal{E} is then computed as:

$$\mathcal{E} = \bigcup_{i=1}^T \Phi(p_i), \quad \text{with} \quad \Phi(p_i) \perp \Phi(p_j) \quad \forall i \neq j \quad (1)$$

This approach allows the computation time of EMF coverage to scale nearly linearly with the number of threads. In our experimental setup, we observe a linear performance improvement factor increasing the number of threads, with diminishing returns only occurring due to hardware limitations, such as memory bandwidth or CPU scheduling overhead, as shown in Tables II and III.

3.2 Quadtree Indexing of TX Locations

A major computational bottleneck in large-scale EMF simulations is the identification, for each pixel, of the set of transmitting antennas (TXs) that can contribute to its received field strength. A naive linear scan over all 5G TXs for each pixel leads to a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(N_{\text{pix}} \cdot N_{\text{TX}})$, which is unfeasible for national-scale simulations. To address this challenge and effectively identify which transmitting antennas illuminate each pixel in the simulation region, the proposed framework utilises a quad-tree spatial algorithm for organising the transmitting antennas database. The quadtree indexing scheme implemented in the TX database is a recursive hierarchical spatial data structure that systematically decomposes the two-dimensional domain into a hierarchy

of nested square regions, enabling efficient spatial partitioning and query operations [10–13]. The proposed framework implements an extended version of the traditional quadtree paradigm—referred to as the *GeoQuadTree*—which adapts the original Cartesian-based structure [14] to operate on geospatial coordinates of TX antennas. This customised variant [15] incorporates several enhancements to enable efficient and scalable processing of geospatial data in large-scale wireless network environments:

- *Geographic Bounding with Degree-Based Coordinates.* The *GeoQuadTree* operates in geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude), explicitly accounting for Earth’s curvature. This is achieved via adaptive conversion from meters to degrees, using dynamic scaling based on the cosine of the latitude to ensure accurate region partitioning at different latitudes.
- *Minimum Cell Size and Adaptive Subdivision.* The *GeoQuadTree* maintains a configurable minimum spatial resolution, *min-span-degrees*, to prevent excessive subdivision in densely populated nodes. This mitigates the typical drawbacks of traditional uniform quadtree methods, such as excessive memory consumption and unnecessary recursion.
- *Hybrid Distance Evaluation in Range Queries.* The *GeoQuadTree* employs a dual-phase approach for spatial queries: an initial rapid bounding-box prefilter, followed by a hybrid distance assessment utilising a planar approximation for distances up to 5 km, switching to the simplified Haversine formula (see 3.3) for greater distances. This hybrid model optimises both precision and efficiency, in contrast to conventional quadtrees that depend solely on bounding-box intersections.
- *Optimized Insertion and Approximate Coincidence Check.* The *GeoQuadTree* insertion algorithm incorporates duplicate-aware logic to prevent unnecessary subdivisions for nearly identical points by applying an epsilon-threshold, thus enhancing efficiency in densely populated urban areas with co-located base stations.

An illustration of the *GeoQuadTree* scheme built from a real-world 5G base station dataset is shown in Fig.1.

Given a pixel centre p and a maximum search radius d , the *GeoQuadTree* ensures the efficient retrieval of all TXs within distance d from p , enabling near real-time electromagnetic field computations even over vast territories. It accomplishes this by excluding entire branches of the search tree outside the query region, reducing the complexity to $\mathcal{O}(\log N_{\text{TX}} + k)$, where k is the number of TXs in the query area.

Let \mathcal{Q} denote the quadtree, and $\text{query}(\mathcal{Q}, p, d)$ the set of 5G/6G TXs retrieved for pixel p . The maximum field contribution received in p can be identified as :

$$E_b(p) = \max_{t \in \text{query}(\mathcal{Q}, p, d)} \mathcal{E}(p, t) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{E}(p, t)$ is the electric field intensity at pixel p due to transmitter t , according to the selected propagation model. Equation (2) identifies the *best server* from transmitting antennas for pixel p and is a conservative estimate of the received field strength, which is often used for a quick screening of 5G coverage. Alternatively, the suggested framework can provide the vector containing the electric field contributions at each pixel p :

$$\mathbf{E}(p) = [\mathcal{E}(p, t)]_{t \in \text{query}(\mathcal{Q}, p, d)} \quad (3)$$

This vector facilitates computing the *exposure index* compared to regulatory limits.

In the tests conducted for the electromagnetic field (EMF) coverage evaluation across the entire Italian territory—considering all 5G transmitters deployed by all national operators—the proposed *GeoQuadTree* implementation demonstrated high computational performance and scalability. Specifically, the following characteristics were observed:

Figure 1: Illustration of GeoQuadTree indexing scheme for 5G TXs data

- Memory occupancy of approximately ~ 1 KB per point;
- Insertion throughput: $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ operations/sec;
- Query throughput: $\sim 10^5 - 2.5 \times 10^5$ operations/sec, depending on TX density.

3.3 Algebraic Simplifications

Sampling the elevation profile along the TX-RX path, performed over the Earth's surface with angular resolution $\Delta\beta$, is the function with the greatest computational impact, accounting for approximately 65% of the total execution time. This process involves evaluating terrain heights at multiple angles to reconstruct the vertical propagation profile, and requires intensive use of transcendental functions such as $\sin()$ and $\cos()$, repeated millions of times.

A calculation system is therefore implemented based on iterative succession, based on the fact that where $\beta_i = i * \Delta\beta$ can be replaced with $\beta_i = \beta_{i-1} + \Delta\beta$ and by pre-calculating $\cos(\Delta\beta)$ and $\sin(\Delta\beta)$, we consider for example:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\beta_i) &= \cos(\beta_{i-1} + \Delta\beta) \\ &= \cos(\beta_{i-1})\cos(\Delta\beta) - \sin(\beta_{i-1})\sin(\Delta\beta) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The goal is to replace calls to $\cos()$ and $\sin()$ within the loop with an update based on the values from the previous step. This replaces two calls to trigonometric functions per iteration with a few multiplications and additions, which are generally much faster. The effect is to speed up the calculation of this function up to 15%, and accuracy tests have confirmed its validity.

For the *GeoQuadTree* research engine the Haversine formula have been approximated considering a max radius distance of 250 km from:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \sin^2(\Delta\phi/2) + \cos(\phi_1) * \cos(\phi_2) * \sin^2(\Delta\lambda/2) \\ c &= 4 * \operatorname{atan}^2\left(\frac{\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{a}-1}\right) \\ D &= R_{earth} * c \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

to an approximate formula with an error of maximum 0.0001% within 250 km of evaluation distance:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{approx} &\approx 2 * \sqrt{a} * \left(1 + \frac{a}{6}\right) \\ D &= R_{earth} * c_{approx} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

3.4 Entropic Data Distribution

The default spatial ordering of pixels and their subsequent division into processing tasks often results in an imbalance of workload, due to the correlation between spatial proximity and computational complexity. Contiguous geographic areas typically require a similar number of calculations because a similar set of base station beams illuminates them. At the level of thread pools, this results in specific threads being processed more slowly than others, ultimately increasing the overall simulation time.

To mitigate this issue, the input pixel data is randomly shuffled in advance to promote a more uniform distribution of the computational load across all processing units. This optimisation is particularly beneficial in highly parallelised systems.

In Fig. 2, each green rectangle represents a pixel assigned to a generic worker(*thread*), while the grey lines indicate the transmitters illuminating each pixel. Despite the balanced pixel allocation, the computational load can vary significantly due to differences in the number of base station beams incident on each pixel. For example, *Worker 3* handles a much higher number of transmitters than *Worker 1*. The imbalance is addressed by distributing pixels entropically

Figure 2: Threads Pool and entropic distribution

to parallel workers, ensuring a more even computational load. As the number of transmitters per pixel cannot be predicted in advance, the entropic method provides a reliable solution for large-scale simulations.

4 HPC Design for Scalable 5G/6G Coverage Computation

4.1 Input and Output of HPC 5G Simulator

The 5G/6G coverage simulation tool uses two databases:

- *Pixel Database*: Represents the simulation area as a regular grid of $100\text{m} \times 100\text{m}$ squares, each containing data such as population, Corine land cover and SRTM elevation model.
- *5G/6G Sector Database*: Contains information on radio sectors (over 100k), including location, antenna parameters (e.g., height, power, gain, azimuth, tilt), frequency, and pattern, allowing accurate positioning of radio sources within the simulation area.

The output of simulation tool is stored in an optimised data structure to support subsequent aggregation, visualisation, and regulatory compliance analysis.

4.2 Simulator Architecture and Parallel Implementation

The simulator design took advantage of object-oriented multithreading (OOP) and was developed in C++ (ISO C++17 standard). Temporal complexity was reduced both in the computation core—through the adoption of concurrent process groups (thread pools) [16]—and in the I/O and logging subsystems, which handle result saving and diagnostic output asynchronously. The tool was compiled with optimization flags to exploit instruction-level parallelism and vectorisation features available in modern CPU architectures [17, 18].

The *main Thread* orchestrates the simulation by initialising the environment, reading input data, and dividing the workload across available threads. It is organized into four functional components (Fig. 3): *Data Loading*, *Work Dispatching*, *Thread Synchronisation*, and *Log Buffer Writing*. These components operate following the multithreaded execution paradigm, managing available system resources (CPU cores, threads per core, memory, file system) to achieve optimal throughput and minimize contention.

Each worker thread computes radio coverage for a designated subset of receiver pixels and executes the following tasks:

- Retrieve all transmitting base stations located within the maximum simulation distance from the current receiver pixel by querying the GeoQuadTree spatial index.

Figure 3: Simulator architecture

- For each detected base station, compute the propagation and path loss according to ITU-R models. This includes evaluating the diffraction loss, the elevation profile corrected for Earth curvature, and the specific antenna gains in both horizontal and vertical planes.
- If required by the simulation settings, identify the base station providing the highest received power (best server) and store the associated performance metrics.
- Write the computed results to output files, either for each base station or only for the best server, depending on the initial configuration settings.

This multithreaded design enables the *HPC 5G simulator* to scale efficiently with the number of CPU threads, achieving high performance even when evaluating complex propagation scenarios across millions of pixels.

5 Performance Evaluation and Benchmarking

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of the proposed *5G/6G coverage simulator*. The analysis focuses on execution time, scalability, and computational efficiency, using two high-performance computing platforms with distinct hardware configurations. Table 1 reports the technical specifications of the servers employed to assess the impact of hardware architecture on the framework’s performance.

5.1 Roofline Model Analysis

The performance of the *HPC 5G Coverage Simulator* was analysed using the Roofline model to evaluate its computational efficiency relative to the theoretical performance bounds of the underlying hardware. Fig. 4 shows that, for Server A, the *HPC 5G coverage simulator* (blue

Table 1: Technical Specifications of the Multicore Servers

Component	Server A	Server B
CPU	Intel i9-10850K	AMD EPYC 7502
Freq. (GHz)	5.20	3.35
Cores / Threads	10 / 20	64 / 128
L3 Cache (MB)	20	128
GFLOPS	576	1280
RAM (GB)	64 DDR4	512 DDR4
Storage (GB)	M.2 SSD 1000	M.2 SSD 2000
OS	Ubuntu 20.04	Ubuntu 22.04
Instr. Set	SSE4.2, AVX2, AVX512	SSE4.2, AVX2
GPU	RTX A5000	A100
CUDA Cores	8192	6912
Memory	24 GB GDDR6	40 GB HBM2
Bus Width	384-bit	5120-bit

point) approaches the performance ceiling defined by the SATA M.2 bandwidth. This indicates that the application is predominantly I/O-bound, i.e. limited by disk throughput rather than computational capacity. In contrast, the *serial 5G coverage simulator* (red point) performs significantly below the machine’s hardware limits, highlighting inefficiencies in computational execution and memory utilisation.

The rightward shift of the HPC implementation along the arithmetic intensity axis indicates a better balance between computation and memory access. This effectively mitigates memory bandwidth bottlenecks. Adopting multithreading has led to significant increases in processing throughput and cache utilisation, reducing computational latency and improving overall efficiency. Furthermore, profiling results indicate a 91.4% reduction in energy consumption [19], highlighting the advantages of parallelisation in terms of both speed and energy efficiency.

Figure 4: Roofline model for Server A: parallel vs serial performance

5.2 Scalability Testing

The software architecture of the proposed 5G coverage simulator was designed for scalability across multiple processing cores. To validate this property, a series of benchmarks were con-

ducted to measure the execution time for large-scale scenarios comprising up to 50,000 transmitting antennas and either 10^7 or 3×10^7 pixels, with a search radius of 10 km. The number of active threads (N_{threads}) was varied to assess parallel performance scaling.

Fig. 5-6 presents the speedup curves when using the version of the tool with entropic and algebraic optimisation activated (orange line), multithreaded entropic only (green line) and standard baseline multithread (blue line). In Fig. 5 the Server A (Intel i9), which features 10 physical cores and Hyper-Threading (HT) support, present a near-linear performance increase up to $N_{\text{threads}} = 10$, corresponding to the physical core count. For $N_{\text{threads}} > 10$, HT is enabled, yielding continued albeit reduced performance gains due to control overhead. The inflexion point at $N_{\text{threads}} = 11$ indicates the onset of HT-related saturation effects, as predicted in Intel’s scalability studies [17].

Figure 5: Performance vs. Number of Threads on Server A

Figure 6 shows the analogous benchmark for Server B (dual AMD EPYC), which supports up to 128 hardware threads with an accelerated factor up to $154.8\times$.

Comparison with Alternative Spatial Indexing Methods

5.3 Comparison with Alternative Spatial Indexing Methods

To further assess the performance of the proposed *GeoQuadTree* indexing scheme, a comparative evaluation was conducted against two widely adopted spatial data structures: the *R-Tree* (based on bounding-volume hierarchies) [20, 21] and the *KD-Tree* [22, 23] (a binary space-partitioning structure). These algorithms were selected as representative baselines of hierarchical spatial search and binary tree-based methods, respectively.

The *Boost R-Tree*, implemented in the *Boost.Geometry* library [24], organizes transmitter locations into minimum bounding rectangles, providing efficient range and nearest-neighbor queries with average complexity of $\mathcal{O}(\log N)$. The *KD-Tree*, initially proposed by Bentley [25], recursively partitions the dataset along coordinate axes, achieving compact memory usage and good performance for low-dimensional nearest-neighbour searches.

Figure 7 reports the performance scaling on the *Intel i9* server for the three indexing strategies as a function of the number of threads. The *same test case used in the previous benchmarks* was adopted here to ensure consistent conditions. Specifically, a series of benchmarks was conducted to measure the execution time for large-scale scenarios comprising up to 50,000 transmitting antennas and either 10^7 or 3×10^7 pixels, with a search radius of 10 km.

Figure 6: Performance vs. Number of Threads on Server B

The *GeoQuadTree* exhibits superior scalability and throughput across the full thread range. In particular:

- At 10 threads (physical core saturation), *GeoQuadTree* achieves a $+10\%$ performance gain over the Boost R-Tree and $+120\%$ over the KD-Tree.
- Beyond 10 threads, Hyper-Threading still yields measurable benefits, with *GeoQuadTree* reaching a $39.4\times$ speedup at 20 threads, compared with $35.9\times$ for the Boost R-Tree and $17.7\times$ for the KD-Tree.
- The performance advantage is mainly attributed to *GeoQuadTree*'s *adaptive geodetic subdivision* and *hybrid planar/Haversine distance evaluation*, which avoid redundant bounding-box checks and minimize trigonometric computations in query loops.

GeoQuadTree offers nearly steady memory usage alongside its superior raw throughput. In contrast, R-Tree demonstrates heightened fragmentation with denser datasets, and KD-Tree faces elevated insertion costs due to its rebalancing processes.

In summary, the introduced *GeoQuadTree* surpasses traditional binary and bounding-volume indexing frameworks in terms of computational scalability and geographic precision. Its explicit latitude–longitude adaptation and distance-aware pruning make it particularly suitable for large-scale *5G/6G EMF simulations*, where transmitter distributions span several hundred kilometres and millions of query points.

5.4 Impact of Thread Count and Pixel Volume on Runtime

Tables 2 and 3 report the detailed execution times for various configurations on Server A and Server B, respectively. Each test includes different processing strategies that take into account all the optimisation previously explained, only the randomisation of the input pixels and the standard multithreaded non-optimised (All Optimisation, Entropic, Ordered) and thread counts. The sequential case serves as a baseline for performance normalisation.

In particular, execution times grow sublinearly with respect to the size of the problem, demonstrating the effectiveness of the modular and parallel architecture of the framework. The sub-linear growth in execution time observed when scaling from 10^7 to 3×10^7 pixels confirms the

Figure 7: Spatial indexing performance scaling on the server A (Intel i9 cpu). GeoQuadTree outperforms R-Tree and KD-Tree in scalability and throughput.

Processor Intel i9 10850K @ 3.6GHz - 50k Tx Sectors				
			10 ⁷ Pixels	3 * 10 ⁷ Pixels
Strategy	Max Threads	Num. Threads	Elab. Time (sec.)	Elab. Time (sec.)
Algebraic Opt + Entropic Multithreaded	20	20	71.0 s.	172.5 s.
	20	16	87.5 s.	206.5 s.
	20	12	106.0 s.	246.4 s.
	20	8	119.0 s.	277.0 s.
	20	4	234.0 s.	547.1 s.
Entropic Multithreaded	20	20	78.0 s.	193.0 s.
	20	16	97.0 s.	228.5 s.
	20	12	116.5 s.	277.0 s.
	20	8	130.5 s.	311.5 s.
	20	4	255 s.	610.1 s.
Multithreaded Baseline	20	20	135.2 s.	
	20	16	155.0 s.	
	20	12	170.5 s.	
	20	8	162.5 s.	
	20	4	264.5 s.	
Sequential Code	20	1	2800 s.	6777 s.

Table 2: Simulation execution times on Server A

efficiency of the framework’s parallelization strategy. Notably, full-scale simulations over the entire Italian territory can be completed in less than 45 seconds on Server B, highlighting the system’s suitability for national-scale EMF assessments.

Processor Dual AMD EPYC 7502 @ 2.5GHz - 50k Tx Sectors				
			10 ⁷ Pixels	3 * 10 ⁷ Pixels
Strategy	Max Threads	Num. Threads	Elab. Time (sec.)	Elab. Time (sec.)
Algebraic Opt + Entropic Multithreaded	128	128	18.0 s.	42.5 s.
	128	96	20.6 s.	51.0 s.
	128	64	23.5 s.	57.5 s.
	128	32	44.0 s.	105.5 s.
	128	16	89.0 s.	210.0 s.
	128	8	164.0 s.	404.6 s.
Entropic Multithreaded	128	128	21 s.	46.5 s.
	128	96	22.5 s.	56.5 s.
	128	64	26.0 s.	62.5 s.
	128	32	46.0 s.	114.5 s.
	128	16	96.5 s.	230.5 s.
	128	8	182.8 s.	437.7 s.
Multithreaded Baseline	128	128	85.5 s.	
	128	96	105.0 s.	
	128	64	110.5 s.	
	128	32	122.5 s.	
	128	16	144.5 s.	
	128	8	178.5 s.	
Sequential Code	128	1	2786 s.	7503 s.

Table 3: Simulation execution times on Server B

6 Conclusions

This work presents a high-performance computing tool for the large-scale simulation of 5G/6G coverage. It is designed to address the computational bottlenecks of traditional radio propagation tools. Significant improvements in computational speed are achieved when considering extensive territorial areas through the integration of parallel processing, multithreading, GeoQuadTree-based spatial indexing and the simplification of algebraic expressions. Benchmarking results demonstrate near-linear scalability across CPU threads, with execution time reductions of over two orders of magnitude compared to non-parallel, non-multithreaded implementations. Notably, full-scale 5G coverage evaluations of Italy can be completed in under one minute, confirming the system’s suitability for national-scale coverage analysis and regulatory assessments. Using a variety of ITU propagation models to calculate coverage up to 26 GHz makes the proposed simulator adaptable to the evolving requirements of 6G. Future developments can be focused on integrating GPU-based acceleration and real-time data ingestion to support dynamic simulation scenarios and enable integration into digital twin ecosystems for network planning.

Acknowledgment

This work was carried out within the framework of a project between the Ministry of “Imprese Made in Italy” and Fondazione Ugo Bordoni.

References

- [1] E. Commission, “5G for europe: An action plan,” Brussels, COM(2016) 588 Final, 14.9.2016.
- [2] K. Kapusniak, T. Nautiyal, and R. Grammenos, “Accelerating and improving simulation performance in communication systems modeling through parallel computing and clustering,” *Journal of Student Research*, vol. 9, Jan. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jsr.org/index.php/path/article/view/829>
- [3] NASA, “Nasa shuttle radar topography mission global 3 arc second,” <https://doi.org/10.5067/MEASURES/SRTM/SRTMGL3.003>, NASA JPL, 2013.
- [4] ITU-R, “Sm-2028-2 - monte carlo simulation methodology for the use in sharing and compatibility studies between different radio services or systems,” ITU, Tech. Rep., Jun 2017.
- [5] COST, “Cost 231 final - digital mobile radio towards future generation systems,” Chap4, Tech. Rep., 1996.
- [6] ITU-R, “M.2412-0 - guidelines for evaluation of radio interface technologies for imt-2020,” ITU, Tech. Rep., Oct 2017.
- [7] —, “P.526-11 - propagation by diffraction,” ITU, Tech. Rep., Oct 2009.
- [8] F. Mangiatordi and E. Pallotti, “A gpu accelerated framework for monitoring lte/5g interference to dvb-t systems,” in *2021 AEIT International Annual Conference (AEIT)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [9] M. Bamell, N. Stokes, J. Steeger, and J. Grabowski, “Ultra-high fidelity radio frequency propagation modeling using distributed high performance graphical processing units: A simulator for multi-element non-stationary antenna systems,” in *2017 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference (HPEC)*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [10] K. Park, “A hierarchical binary quadtree index for spatial queries,” *Wireless Networks*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1913–1929, 2019.
- [11] R. K. Harle, “Spatial indexing for location-aware systems,” in *2007 Fourth Annual International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Systems: Networking & Services (MobiQuitous)*. IEEE, 2007, pp. 1–8.
- [12] F. Garcia-Garcia, A. Corral, and L. Iribarne, “Including the quadtree index in spatialhadoop,” in *Proceedings of the 24th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics*, ser. PCI ’20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2021, p. 376–379. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3437120.3437344>
- [13] R. T. Liu, Y. J. Chen, D. Y. Cao, and D. Y. Liu, “A new quadtree-based skyline query algorithm,” in *Electronic Engineering and Information Science*, ser. Advanced Materials Research, vol. 981. Trans Tech Publications Ltd, 8 2014, pp. 175–178.
- [14] R. Finkel and J. Bentley, “Quad trees: A data structure for retrieval on composite keys.” *Acta Inf.*, vol. 4, pp. 1–9, 03 1974.
- [15] EP, “Geoquadtree,” <https://github.com/fondazionebordoni/geoquadtree>, FUB, 2025.
- [16] W. Antony, *C++ Concurrency in action*. MANNING, 2019.
- [17] Intel, “Hyper-threading technology architecture and microarchitecture,” *Intel Technology Journal*, vol. VI, 2002.

- [18] “Skylake s,” Available:<https://tinyurl.com/skylake-s>, Intel, Tech. Rep., 2022.
- [19] “Likwid,” <https://hpc.fau.de/research/tools/likwid/>, NHR-FAU, 2025.
- [20] A. Guttman, “R-trees: A dynamic index structure for spatial searching,” in *Proceedings of the 1984 ACM SIGMOD international conference on Management of data*, 1984, pp. 47–57.
- [21] T. Vu and A. Eldawy, “R*-Grove: Balanced Spatial Partitioning for Large-scale Datasets,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.11651>
- [22] I. Šimeček, C. Kozický, D. Langr, and P. Tvrđík, “Space-efficient k-d tree-based storage format for sparse tensors,” in *Proceedings of the 29th International Symposium on High-Performance Parallel and Distributed Computing*, ser. HPDC ’20. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2020, p. 29–33. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3369583.3392692>
- [23] M. Skrodzki, “The k-d tree data structure and a proof for neighborhood computation in expected logarithmic time,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.04936>
- [24] “Boost.geometry — boost.geometry spatial index,” accessed: 2025-07-01. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/boostorg/geometry/tree/boost-1.89.0>
- [25] J. L. Bentley, “Multidimensional binary search trees used for associative searching,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 18, no. 9, pp. 509–517, 1975.